

Liquid Phase Exfoliation of Arsenic Trisulfide (As_2S_3) Nanosheets and Their Use as Anodes in Potassium Ion Batteries

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ABSTRACT

Here we demonstrate the production of 2D nanosheets of arsenic disulfide (As_2S_3) via liquid phase exfoliation of the naturally occurring mineral, orpiment. The resultant nanosheets had mean lateral dimensions and thickness of 400 nm and 10 nm respectively and had structure indistinguishable from the bulk. The nanosheets were solution mixed with carbon nanotubes and cast into nanocomposite films for use as anodes in potassium ion batteries. These anodes exhibited outstanding electrochemical performance, demonstrating an impressive discharge capacity of 619 mAh/g at a current density of 50 mA/g. Even after 1000 cycles at 500 mA/g, the anodes retained an impressive 94% of their capacity. Quantitative analysis of the rate-performance yielded a capacity at very low rate of 838 mAh/g, about two thirds of the theoretical capacity of As_2S_3 (1305 mAh/g). However, this analysis also implied As_2S_3 to have a very small solid-state diffusion coefficient ($\sim 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$), somewhat limiting its potential for high-rate applications.

KEYWORDS. *Two-dimensional materials, arsenic disulfide, liquid phase exfoliation, nanosheets, K-ion battery anodes, rate performance.*

INTRODUCTION

The escalating global demand for energy storage solutions, driven by the widespread popularity of portable electronic devices,¹ the rise of electric vehicles,² and the integration of renewable energy sources³ has contributed to the development of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) as today's predominant energy storage technology.^{3,4} However, the relentless expansion of battery usage has highlighted the limited global supply of lithium.⁵ In turn, this has raised concerns regarding the vulnerability of our dependence on lithium, prompting a re-evaluation of our energy storage approaches.^{5,6} In this context, the spotlight has turned to developing viable alternatives to lithium ion batteries. In particular, much attention has been given to batteries based on sodium and potassium ions due to their chemical similarity to lithium.⁷⁻⁹ Compared to lithium, sodium and potassium are abundant elements and their use in batteries would enhance sustainability, and accessibility.^{9,10}

While substantial progress has been achieved in the domain of sodium-ion batteries (SIBs),^{11,12} the development of potassium-ion batteries (KIBs) is less mature.^{8,13,14} There is still a pressing need to develop and characterize new materials for use as both cathodes¹⁵ and anodes¹⁶ in KIBs. For over a decade, the broad family of two-dimensional (2D) layered materials has shown immense promise for use in both LIB and SIB electrodes.^{17,18} More recently, these materials have been utilized in the pursuit of new potassium-storing anode materials.¹⁹ The appeal of 2D materials for use in anodes derives from various attributes. For example, the family of 2D materials is very diverse, containing >2000 known materials, each with distinct properties and capabilities.²⁰ This huge materials choice increases the probability of discovering a material with the right combination of properties to meet the specific demands of KIBs. In addition, the ability to convert layered materials into nanosheets via liquid exfoliation^{21,22} and subsequently to control their dimensions via size-selection protocols,²³ enables a high degree of processability, allowing us to produce electrodes with controlled properties.^{24,25} Finally, we might expect diffusion of ions within the inter-layer channels in 2D materials to be faster than in 3-dimensional materials, leading to better rate-performance and enhanced power density.²⁴⁻²⁶

Thus, while 2D materials are very attractive for use in KIBs, only a fraction of the vast array of possible 2D materials has been explored.¹⁹ The quest for high-capacity electrodes has led to a focus on phosphorous- or sulfur-rich materials such as black phosphorus (b-P, theoretical capacity=864 mAh/g,²⁷), tin sulfide (SnS₂, 733 mAh/g,²⁸), molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂, 670

mAh/g,^{29, 30}), antimony trisulfide (Sb_2S_3 , 946 mAh/g,^{31, 32}) or bismuth trisulfide (Bi_2S_3 , 625 mAh/g,³³). These materials represent just a handful of those capable of delivering high specific capacities in KIBs. It is very likely that various other layered materials exist with the potential to deliver capacities comparable to those already studied. A comprehensive literature search identifies As_2S_3 , found naturally as the mineral orpiment,³⁴ as a previously unexfoliated layered material. It is a compositional analog of the well-known and previously exfoliated 2D materials³⁵ Sb_2S_3 and Bi_2S_3 and has significant potential for ion storage in battery electrodes (theoretical capacity 1305 mAh/g, see below). However, to our knowledge, no reports exist on using it in battery electrode applications.

Although arsenic is indeed toxic, especially in its inorganic, trivalent form³⁶, it is still widely used in a range of industries including textiles, wood preservation, semiconductor growth and the production of lead-acid batteries.³⁷ In any case, irrespective of the possibility for its use in real applications, from the perspective of basic science it is important to study its potential as an ion storing electrode material. Indeed, such studies have previously been carried out both on elemental arsenic³⁸ as well as arsenic containing compounds.³⁹

In this paper, we explore As_2S_3 nanosheets as an anode material for KIBs. We demonstrate that orpiment can be easily exfoliated in liquids to give nanosheets in reasonable quantities. Using single walled carbon nanotubes as binder, As_2S_3 nanosheets can easily be solution cast into films for use as K-ion anodes. Electrochemical characterization shows these anodes to demonstrate capacities as high as 619 mAh/g and exceptional capacity retention over 1000 charge-discharge cycles.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Few-layered As_2S_3 exfoliation and characterization

As_2S_3 exists as a naturally occurring layered crystal, orpiment, as shown in Figure 1A.^{40, 41} These yellowish crystals belong to the family of 2D layered materials.^{40, 41} The crystal structure of As_2S_3 belongs to the space group $\text{P}2_1/\text{n}$ and has a monoclinic lattice structure.⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴ Each single layer is made up of AsS_3 pyramids linked together by strong As-S-As covalent bonds with weak Van der Waals inter-layer interactions as shown in Figure 1B.⁴⁵ The unit cell contains 20 atoms distributed

over two monolayers (Figure 1B).^{41, 44, 45} An SEM image of the orpiment crystal surface, as shown in Figure 1C, confirms the layered morphology.

An orpiment crystal was first cleaned and converted to powder via bath sonication in the solvent 2-propanol (details of cleaning and liquid-phase exfoliation process is given in the method section). Inert atmosphere liquid phase exfoliation (LPE) was performed by bath sonicating the resultant powder for 10 hours in dried, distilled, and de-gassed 2-propanol under an argon-atmosphere. The resultant dispersion was centrifuged to remove large unexfoliated material (220g) and again to remove any very small particles (3800g) resulting in a standard dispersion (Figure 1D). The concentration (C) of the dispersion was determined to be 1 mg/ml via filtration of 1 ml of dispersion and mass weighing.

To investigate the optical properties of the dispersed nanosheets, optical extinction spectroscopy was employed, as shown in Figure 1E. The extinction spectrum ($\text{Ext}=-\log T$) was obtained and subsequently converted into an extinction coefficient spectrum ($\epsilon=\text{Ext}/Cl$, where l is the cuvette length),⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹ As depicted in Figure 1E, the extinction coefficient spectrum exhibits a steady increase with decreasing wavelength with no clear optical absorption band-edge. The lack of a clear bandedge in nanosheet dispersions is generally due to light scattering.⁴⁸ To address this, scattering coefficient spectra (σ) were measured (Figure 1E) using an integrating sphere, and then subtracted from the extinction coefficient spectrum (ϵ) to obtain the absorption coefficient spectrum (α).^{46, 48, 49} The α -spectrum shows a clear band-edge at $\lambda = 500$ nm, corresponding to an optical gap of 2.5 eV. This is consistent with bandgap values of ~ 2.5 eV associated with As_2S_3 , as reported in the literature.^{41, 42, 44}

Furthermore, transmission electron microscopy was utilized to characterize the dispersion. TEM images, as presented in Figure 1F reveal the presence of As_2S_3 nanosheets with a mean length ($\langle L \rangle$) of approximately 350 nm. Raman spectroscopy was also employed to characterize the intermolecular vibrations. Figure 1G presents the Raman spectra of both bulk and exfoliated As_2S_3 . These spectra exhibit distinct, well-defined sharp phonon modes which can be categorized into two distinct regions: Region I spans from wavenumber 120-210 cm^{-1} , while region II encompasses wavenumber from 280-390 cm^{-1} . Raman phonon peaks in region I at 135 cm^{-1} , 154 cm^{-1} , 179 cm^{-1} , and 202 cm^{-1} correspond to the bond-bending vibrations, while the phonon peaks in region II at 291 cm^{-1} , 310 cm^{-1} , 354 cm^{-1} , and 382 cm^{-1} correspond to bond-stretching vibrations.⁴³⁻⁴⁵ The

phonon modes of bulk and exfoliated As_2S_3 , are the same within the resolution of the Raman spectrometer used in this study and are in alignment with literature data,^{41, 43, 44} showing that exfoliation does not change the material structure. In addition, no extra Raman modes were detected, confirming that As_2S_3 nanosheets are free from impurities and did not undergo oxidation during the exfoliation process.

To gain an understanding of the crystal structure of As_2S_3 few-layered nanosheets, we employ both X-ray diffraction (XRD) and selected area electron-diffraction (SAED) through TEM. Figure 2A shows the XRD pattern of the bulk crystal and exfoliated As_2S_3 nanosheets in the 2θ range from 15° to 65° . The diffraction pattern of the bulk crystal displayed several peaks at different angles, including $2\theta = 18.5^\circ, 22.2^\circ, 28.0^\circ, 29.0^\circ, 37.5^\circ, 38.4^\circ, 43.3^\circ, 45.3^\circ, 48.1^\circ, 52.3^\circ, 57.7^\circ, 57.9^\circ,$ and 62.6° . These peaks were assigned to various hkl planes in the reciprocal lattice space of the monoclinic crystal structure of As_2S_3 , such as (020), (-101), (021), (130), (040), (140), (041), (-202), (150), (051), (060), (042), and (161). It was observed that these peaks were closely aligned with the reference data for orpiment (PDF 01-071-2435), and no impurity phases were detected. A significant preferred orientation was observed, as the (0 2 0) diffraction peak was approximately three times more intense than the next highest peak. Indicating, this plane is parallel to the alignment of layers along the b-axis in the orpiment crystal structure (which is also parallel to the cleavage plane). The highest intensity of this peak strongly suggests that the powdered sample particles predominantly took on a platelet shape, rather than a spherical form.⁵⁰ The finding is in line with similar patterns that have been previously reported in the existing literature.⁵¹ For the exfoliated nanomaterials, the presence of only the (0 2 0) peak is a clear indication of their two-dimensional morphology.⁵⁰ It is worth noting that, the exfoliated nanosheets are not expected to perfectly restack like the bulk material, resulting in a distinct XRD pattern compared to the bulk material,⁵⁰ therefore, As_2S_3 is also expected to behave the same.” The broad XRD peak at 2θ position 32.5° corresponds to the silicon (002) substrate.⁵² TEM imaging of a few-layered thick nanosheet (Figure 2B) allowed measurement of a SAED pattern (Figure 2C) showing the presence of well-defined sharp diffraction spots. The diffraction spot pattern is fully indexed (Figure S1, supplementary information) with the monoclinic lattice structure of As_2S_3 with nanosheet orientation in the [010] direction. Thus, representing towards the high crystallinity of exfoliated nanosheets of As_2S_3 . Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) conducted on As_2S_3 nanosheets confirms the presence of As and S elements (Figure S2, supplementary information). Notably,

oxygen is absent in the elemental EDX scans, confirming that the nanosheets formed by inert gas LPE are anhydrous. The average atomic ratio calculated over 24 randomly selected nanoplatelets reveals $\langle S/As \rangle = 1.5$.

Additionally, we employ atomic force microscopy (AFM) to examine the distribution of length (L), thickness (t), and aspect-ratio (L/t) of exfoliated nanosheets. Figure 2D shows an AFM image displaying several nanosheets with varying sizes, and thicknesses. For each individual nanosheet, length and apparent thickness were measured. Apparent thickness values were converted into real thickness (t) by measuring the step height (Figure S3, supplementary information) as described in detail in the section A of supplementary information. The length, and thickness distribution of 100 nanosheets are presented in Figure 2E, with mean value represented as $\langle L \rangle = 394 \pm 16$ nm, and $\langle t \rangle = 9.8 \pm 0.4$ nm, along with standard errors. Additionally, we calculate the aspect ratio of each nanosheet by taking the ratio of length to its thickness, and plot as shown in Figure 2F. The mean aspect-ratio is found to be 40 ± 3 , which is at the upper end for nanosheets obtained from liquid-phase exfoliation of 2D materials,^{48,53} implying that the ratio of fracture (in-plane) to delamination (out-of-plane) energies is relatively large for this material.⁵³

Electrochemical storage of K^+ ions in As_2S_3 anodes

Previous research has consistently shown that utilizing active materials in the form of 2D-nanosheets within lithium- or sodium-storing battery electrodes leads to near-theoretical capacities.²⁵ This is especially the case when single walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) are used as a replacement for both conductive additives and polymeric binders.⁵⁴ In this composite electrode architecture, SWCNTs establish a mechanically robust and electrically conductive network that enhances charge delivery.^{54,55} This, in turn, allows for the optimization of capacity, rate capability, and cyclability.⁵⁴ We anticipate that the success of this architecture for lithium and sodium storing electrodes can be extended to potassium-storage. Due to its lower density, we might expect As_2S_3 to yield higher specific capacity for potassium-storing anodes as compared to its analogs Sb_2S_3 ($C_{\text{theory}}=946$ mAh/g) and Bi_2S_3 ($C_{\text{theory}}=625$ mAh/g).^{32,33} However, to our knowledge, there are no reports of Li, Na or K-storing electrodes fabricated from As_2S_3 . Here we will explore the potential of nanocomposites consisting of LPE-produced As_2S_3 nanosheets and SWCNTs for developing high-performance K-ion anodes.

Nanocomposites anodes comprising As_2S_3 nanosheets and SWCNTs were fabricated for use in a half-cell configuration. In short, the dispersion of As_2S_3 nanosheets was mixed with a SWCNT dispersion in 2-propanol and then subjected to vacuum filtration onto Celgard 2320 membrane (for detailed procedures, please refer to the method section). This process led to the creation of free-standing nanocomposite films (as shown in the Figure S4 of supplementary information) containing 28-30 weight% nanotubes, without the need for a polymeric binder. Subsequently, the free-standing films were cut into the required dimensions with an area of 0.178 cm^2 for electrochemical testing. The SEM image in Figure 3A, displaying the cross-sectional view of the free-standing As_2S_3 @CNT electrode (total mass-loading 0.44 mg/cm^2), reveals a thickness of $4.6 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. A magnified view of the electrode's surface, as depicted in Figure 3B, reveals a well-connected porous network of 2D nanosheets interlinked with 1D carbon nanotubes. The SEM cross-section image of the composite film, along with the corresponding elemental composition maps, are presented in Figure S4. The EDX spectra of the composite electrode indicate the presence of As and S elements. Elemental maps demonstrate a uniform distribution of As and S elements, with an expected stoichiometry of $\text{As}_2\text{S}_{3.1}$. The electrode porosity was calculated by estimating its density using the thickness and mass loading data, resulting in a density of 0.95 g/cm^3 . Given the densities of As_2S_3 and SWCNT, which are 3.43 g/cm^3 , and 1.8 g/cm^3 respectively, the calculated porosity of the electrode is approximately 67%, similar to but slightly higher than nanosheet-only networks.⁵⁶

Electrochemical characterization was carried out to assess the utility of these electrodes for potassiation/de-potassiation. Figure 3C depicts the cyclic voltammograms (CV) for the first five cycles acquired at a scan rate of 0.1 mV/s in the voltage window between 0.01 and 2.5 V . The CV curve indicates that during the first discharge process a broad cathodic peak appears at 0.75 V , mainly due to the formation of SEI (solid-electrolyte interface) films. This peak disappears in the subsequent sweep cycles. Another peak is seen at 0.08 V , which is likely associated with the alloy reactions between K and As, and is skewed by SEI formation.⁵⁷ From the second cycle, the CV curves follow similar line shapes, and completely overlap demonstrating a highly reversible electrochemical reaction. During the subsequent scans, the cathodic peaks are identified in the overlapping CV curves marked as b1, b2 and b3 and located at 0.81 V , 0.31 V , 0.12 V respectively. Materials with the same structure are known to belong to the same family and are expected to exhibit similar characteristics. Based on the matching stoichiometry, as well as the similar structure

and shape of the CV curves, it is expected that our As_2S_3 electrodes will also demonstrate consistency with the materials from the same family by displaying similar ion storage mechanisms. Therefore, it is predicted that the electrochemical reaction of As_2S_3 with potassium-ion is likely to proceed similarly to that of Bi_2S_3 ⁵⁸ and Sb_2S_3 .^{32, 59} During potassiation, the small cathodic peak at 0.81 V (b1) is attributed to K-ion insertion into As_2S_3 . The second reduction peak at 0.31V (b2) assigned to conversion reaction, i.e., electrochemical reduction of As_2S_3 to arsenic with accompanying the formation of an amorphous K_2S and the third reduction peak centered at 0.12V (b3) can be assigned to alloying reactions between K and arsenic. In addition, during depotassiation, two anodic peaks appear at 0.64 V (a1), and 1.0 V (a2) can be assigned to the dealloying, and further reversible conversion and deintercalation reactions, respectively.^{31-33, 58, 59}

To check the validity of the proposed mechanism, we performed galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments on the As_2S_3 @CNT electrode. Here, both charge and discharge capacities, as well as the current density, were calculated based on the active material (As_2S_3) mass and referred to as Q/M_{act} . In this study, as a part of the initial activation procedure, all electrodes were first subjected to 10 cyclic voltammograms at a scan rate of 0.1 mV/s. This is a reasonably standard activation procedure that allows the formation of a solid electrolyte interface (SEI) layer on the electrode surface. After the activation cycles, we continued cycling the electrode for 200 charge-discharge cycles at the higher current of 200 mA/g. The voltage profiles collected for the first 5 cycles are displayed in Figure 3D with a voltage range of 0.01-2.5 V. During the discharge process, three plateau regions are noticed in the voltage range of 1.2 to 0.8 V (referred to as region I, indicating the intercalation process), 0.75 to 0.45 V (referred to as region II, indicating the conversion process), and 0.45 to 0.07 V (referred to as region III, indicating the alloying reaction). During the charging process, plateau region IV (0.2 to 0.75 V) indicates reverse conversion, while plateau region V (0.8 to 1.2 V) indicates reverse deintercalation reactions. The plateau regions align reasonably well with the peaks observed in the CV curves (Figure 3C).

Figure 3E shows differential voltage plots for the first 5 cycles, which are nearly identical to the peaks observed in the CV curves, but slightly more well-defined. In the first cycle, the GCD curve at 200 mA/g delivers a discharge capacity of 398 mAh/g and a charge capacity of 327 mAh/g. In the subsequent cycles, charge-discharge curves are stable and remain nearly identical, indicating the good stability of the nanostructures as anode materials. Figure 3F illustrates the resulting

charge/discharge capacities of the $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3@\text{CNT}$ electrodes for 200 cycles along with the Coulombic efficiencies (CE). We consider the contribution from carbon nanotubes to the overall measured capacity of $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3@\text{CNT}$ composite electrodes to be negligible due to their very low specific capacity (~ 30 mAh/g), as illustrated in the supplementary information, Figure S5. At the beginning of cycling, the electrodes achieved a CE of 82%. During the following cycles, both the charge and discharge capacities, as well as the CE, gradually increased before reaching their maximum at around 124 cycles. At this point, the discharge and charge capacities reached 468 mAh/g and 466 mAh/g, respectively, with a CE exceeding 99%. Beyond this cycle, the CE remained consistently above 99%, while the discharge and charge capacities levelled off at 459 mAh/g and 457 mAh/g, respectively (refer to Figure S6, supplementary information for the voltage profiles). These findings suggest that contrary to what was previously assumed, the electrode's activation was not fully accomplished within the first five cycles but rather necessitated over 100 cycles to reach its maximum capacity. Similar behavior was also observed by Zhou et al.⁶⁰ in their study of a KIB anode comprised of VS_2 nanosheets. At 500 mA/g current, the specific capacity of the nanostructured VS_2 anode increased from 290 mAh/g to 360 mAh/g after 100 cycles. However, they attributed this phenomenon to an increased wetting of the electrode film by the electrolyte during cycling.⁶⁰ The cycling profile at low current density displayed in Figure 3F demonstrates fluctuating data. This is due to the dissolution of polysulfides (that are formed during the deep potassiation process in majority of metal sulfides) in the electrolyte and its shuttle effect results the loss of active materials, leading to poor reversibility and fluctuating coulombic efficiency. Therefore, this is a significant issue associated with metal sulfides as anodes for KIBs.

To gain a thorough understanding of how activation leads to increased capacity during cycling, the differential voltage plots were analyzed. Such plots are obtained by differentiating the GCD curves (i.e. those used to prepare Figure 3F) and plotted as dQ/dV versus voltage. Figure 4A shows the dQ/dV versus voltage plot for selected cycles for the 5th, 50th, 100th, 124th, 155th, 180th and 200th at a current density of 200 mA/g. The curves collected at different cycles show a noticeable difference when compared to the curve collected at cycle 5. However, after the 124th cycle, all curves overlap each other. This indicates that the activation process is complete after the 124th cycle and the material remains electrochemically stable thereafter.

Following recent research by Nitya et al.,⁶¹ we propose that the electrode undergoes the following reactions at various stages of potential, which we divide into three regions as shown in Figure 4A:

During potassiation:

Region I: at 1.4 to 0.75 V (intercalation process)

Region II: at 0.75 to 0.25 V (conversion reactions)

Region III: at 0.25 to 0.01 V (alloying reactions)

Overall, this reaction is equivalent to

In Figure 4A, two redox peaks are observed in the region (ii), indicating that conversion reaction occurs in two main steps.⁶² The first step (Eq. (2)) involves the creation of amorphous arsenic nanoparticles by reducing As_2S_3 into As and forming K_2S_3 polysulfide (peak R₂ in Figure 4A). These nanosized As particles possess a robust ability to effectively trap the discharge products, thereby preventing the shuttling of byproducts in the electrode surface.⁶³ Consequently, the subsequent reactions (Eq. (3) and Eq. (4)) are accelerated, which is expected to enhance the formation of K_3As , this is clearly seen in Figure 4A as the R₄ peak corresponds to K_3As alloy is intensifying with cycling, remaining stable after 124 cycles. During the charging process, which is also known as depotassiation, the reactions take place reversibly, and the discharge products are consumed to regenerate the original materials. Figure 4A clearly displays these reactions, peak R₅ indicates dealloying at 0.39 V, while the R₆ and R₇ peaks show reverse conversion reactions at 0.48 and 0.58 V. Peak R₈ represents the deintercalation reaction at 0.96 V. In addition, we notice some peak shifts in the dQ/dV curves and the sharpening of the dealloying peak during the activation, have a substantial influence on enhanced charge storage.

To validate our findings, post-mortem analysis of As_2S_3 battery electrodes was performed and the results have been presented in both Figure 4 and Figure S6. To begin with, we examined the CV curves of As_2S_3 @CNT anodes before and after 200 activation cycles to quickly detect any changes in their electrochemical storage properties. The analysis revealed significant changes, as shown in Figure 4B. After extended activation, the voltage hysteresis between conversion and deconversion peaks is reduced to 0.1 V, while intercalation and deintercalation peaks is reduced to 0.06 V. This leads to better reversible electrochemical charge storage, resulting in an enhanced electrochemical K-ion storage capacity. The findings suggest that the discharge products (K_2S_3 and K_2S) can be efficiently trapped by highly active, ultrafine As particles formed in Eq. 2, which significantly reduces the shuttle effect and leads to excellent K-ion charge storage.⁶⁴ Thus, we predict that during activation, amorphous arsenic nanoparticles play a vital role in realizing enhanced charge storage in the charge/discharge process. To evaluate the structural changes in the activated electrode, we performed ex-situ X-ray diffractograms on the potassiated and de-potassiated state of the electrode (Figure 4C). In the potassiated state, the electrode displayed XRD peaks corresponding to the presence of K_3As and K_2S_3 phases, whereas in the de-potassiated state, XRD pattern showed peaks corresponding to only As_2S_3 and CNT, indicating that the structure of the As_2S_3 in As_2S_3 @CNT anodes remains unchanged after cycling. This confirms the above redox reactions of As_2S_3 with K-ions,⁶² implying that a charge equivalent to twelve electrons can be stored per formula unit of As_2S_3 . Thus, the theoretical capacity of As_2S_3 is calculated to be 1305 mAh/g.

To investigate the morphological changes in the activated electrode, SEM imaging was employed. As depicted in Figure 4D, the cross-sectional view of the electrode revealed a clear expansion of 4.6 μm 7.3 μm after 200 cycles. This expansion indicates a reduction in density from 0.95 g/cm^3 to 0.6 g/cm^3 , which in turn implies an increase in porosity from 67% to 79% and internal surface area. After cycling, the electrodes appear smoother with no visible 2D-platelets indicating a uniform and amorphous structure. It is observed that the conversion-type materials undergo a shape alteration upon cycling, and it is highly unlikely for them to retain their original morphology after cycling (Figure 4D). The ex-situ XRD pattern of the electrode which was activated for 200 cycles (see Figure S7), revealed a distinctive broad diffraction peak located at diffraction angles 2θ between 10° - 21° . The presence of this broad peak is a compelling indicator of medium-range ordering in non-crystalline structures of As_2S_3 .⁶⁵ This confirmed the transition of As_2S_3 from

crystalline to non-crystalline phase. It's worth noting that the observed phenomena are in line with the established literature that highlights the amorphization process occurring in both alloy and conversion-type materials during extended cycling, ultimately resulting in the formation of amorphous materials.⁶⁶ After 200 cycles, the SEM-EDX elemental maps were used to analyze the distribution of As and S elements in the cross-sectional film of the $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3/\text{CNT}$ composite electrode to demonstrate its structural stability (Figure S8). After cycling, the electrodes exhibited the distribution of As and S elements, as well as the distribution of K, P, and F from the electrolyte.

After the 200 cycles shown in figure 3F, we performed five charge-discharge cycles at a current density of 50 mA/g, and the resulting voltage profile are displayed in Figure 5A. The overlapping of voltage profiles confirmed a highly reversible electrochemical reaction, signifying the electrode ability to repeatedly transition between charge and discharge states without substantial performance degradation. Notably, we achieved an average discharge capacity of 619 mAh/g and an average charge capacity of 612 mAh/g at 50 mA/g. To comprehensively evaluate the performance, rate-performance tests were performed to assess its capacity and efficiency at different current densities, as depicted in Figure 5B. The data demonstrates the expected falloff in capacity with increasing current. However, when the current density is reduced back to 50 mA/g, an average discharge capacity of 610 mA/g was obtained, indicating excellent reversibility. The impressive nature of As_2S_3 nanosheets lies in their ability to offer a high specific capacity and exceptional reversibility. It is important to emphasize that this low-rate specific capacity exceeds that of almost all other reported 2D materials utilized in KIB anodes across the existing literature (see Table 1, supplementary information). The only higher values we know of are 860 mAh/g (50 mA/g) for $\text{MoS}_{1.5}\text{Se}_{0.5}$ -based electrodes.⁶⁷ Furthermore, the cell consistently maintains a coulombic efficiency exceeding 98% across all tested current densities, indicative of efficient charge transfer, and minimal side-reactions. This underscores the cells capability to mitigate parasitic reactions and prevent capacity degradation.

To assess the cell durability, we examined capacity retention under relatively high current density conditions, subjecting the cell to 1000 charge-discharge cycles at 500 mA/g. In Figure 5C, the initial discharge capacity at the beginning of cycling is 253 mAh/g, gradually decreasing to 237 mAh/g after 1000 cycles. This demonstrates an impressive capacity retention of 94% for this electrode. Notably, this level of retention is exceptional among anodes for KIBs based on 2D

materials (refer to Table S1 in the supplementary information) and is higher than that of similar materials such as Sb₂S₃ and Bi₂S₃-based KIB anodes (refer to Table S2 in the supplementary information). A detailed comparison of the stability and capacity of As₂S₃@CNT anodes with other 2D material-based KIB anodes is presented in Table S1, and with other sulfide-based anodes in Table S2. The electrochemical performance of our As₂S₃@CNT anodes is assessed in Figure 6 by plotting the maximum specific capacity (Q/M_{Act}) against capacity retention and cycle number. Our As₂S₃@CNT anodes exhibit competitive capacity and stability after long cycling when compared to the best-reported results for electrodes based on As₂S₃-analogs, Sb₂S₃, and Bi₂S₃ for KIB. These findings underscore its robust nature and enduring electrochemical performance characteristics. Moreover, when the current density is reduced back to 50 mA/g after 1000 cycles at 500 mA/g, an average discharge capacity of 593 mA/g was obtained, again indicating excellent reversibility and superior potassium storage with greater stability. To achieve sustainable, safe, and long-lasting potassium ion batteries, the use of ether-based electrolytes is promising. By using either green ether-based electrolytes or specific molecular-designed phosphate-based electrolytes, we can significantly enhance the reliability and stability of our electrodes.⁶⁸⁻⁷⁰

Quantitative analysis of rate-performance

Previously, we have shown that one can extract information about the ultimate capacity of electrodes, as well as quantifying the rate performance, via quantitative analysis of capacity versus rate data.⁷¹⁻⁷⁴ This involves plotting the measured specific capacity (Q/M_{Act}) versus charge/discharge rate as shown in Figure 5D. For such analysis, we represent charge/discharge rate via a parameter, R, which is defined as $R = I/Q$, i.e. the specific current divided by the specific capacity measured at that current.^{71, 72, 74-76} This is useful because $1/R$ is a measure of the actual charge/discharge time of the electrode at a given current. This graph shows Q/M_{Act} to decay with rate (R) as is usually observed.^{73, 74}

Such data can be analyzed using various semiempirical fitting equations,⁷⁷ such as that proposed recently by our group:⁷⁴

$$Q / M_{Act} = Q_{M, Act} \left[1 - (R\tau)^n (1 - e^{-(R\tau)^n}) \right] \quad (1)$$

Here, fitting yields three fit parameters: $Q_{M, Act}$, which is the capacity (normalized to active mass) at infinitely low rate; τ , the characteristic charge/discharge time; and n, a parameter which indicates

whether diffusive ($n=0.5$) or capacitive (electrical) ($n=1$) limitations dominate rate performance.⁷¹⁻
⁷⁵ As shown in Figure 5D, this equation fits the experimental data extremely well with fit values: $Q_{M,Act}=832\pm 36$ mAh g⁻¹, $n=0.50\pm 0.01$ and $\tau=2726\pm 360$ s. We will discuss these fit parameters one by one.

The $Q_{M,Act}$ value represents the maximum achievable capacity, measured at infinitely low rate. The fit value (832 ± 36 mAh g⁻¹) about two thirds of the theoretical capacity (1305 mAh/g). This is somewhat lower than previous results which show that exfoliating layered materials to nanosheets which are then combined with carbon nanotubes to yield composite electrodes allows almost full utilization of the active material for storage of Li, Na and K ions.⁷⁸⁻⁸² However, it is consistent with our literature review data (Figure 6 and Table S2) which shows Sb₂S₃-based K-storing electrodes to display 37-65% of theoretical capacity, although Bi₂S₃-based K-storing electrodes showed somewhat higher values (up to 93% of theoretical capacity).

In addition, the n -value is exactly equal to 0.5, indicating that our electrodes are diffusion limited, at least for these thin electrodes (~ 7 μ m after cycling). Probably the most useful parameter is the time constant, τ . This represents the minimum charge/discharge time for the electrode and can be used as a metric for rate performance with higher values of τ indicating poorer rate performance. Our τ -value (2736 s) is large, comparable with the largest reported for 2D-based Li or Na ion batteries (ref⁷³ shows the reported range to be roughly $1s < \tau < 10,000$ s). This indicates very poor rate performance. However, we note that rate-performance in general and the time constant in particular depend very strongly on electrode thickness.^{71, 73, 74} Previously we proposed that a reasonable figure of merit for rate performance is τ / L_E^2 , where L_E is the electrode thickness, with large values indicating poor rate-performance.^{73, 74} This parameter removes some (but not all) of the thickness dependence of τ , especially for electrodes with practically relevant thicknesses (>20 μ m). Taking the post cycling value of $L_E=7.3$ μ m yields $\tau / L_E^2 = 5\times 10^{13}$ s/m². Comparing this to the summary over many Li and Na storing materials reported in ref⁷³ shows this value to be very high for this electrode thickness, indicating that As₂S₃ electrodes have some property that dramatically limits rate performance. Given that the value of $n=0.5$ indicates diffusion limitations suggests that the main culprit might be solid state diffusion in the nanosheets. The timescale associated with solid state diffusion is roughly $\tau_{SSD} = L_{AM}^2 / D_{AM}$ where L_{AM} is the diffusion length

and D_{AM} is the (in-plane) diffusion coefficient within the inter-layer channel. Assuming that τ is dominated by the solid-state diffusion time, we can approximate $\tau_{SSD} = L_{AM}^2 / D_{AM} \sim \tau$. Because τ is the sum of all possible time scales limiting rate performance,⁷⁴ this equation defines the maximum possible value of τ_{SSD} . Taking $L_{AM} \sim 200$ nm (ions only need diffuse from edge to center of the nanosheets), this means D_{AM} is slightly larger than 1.5×10^{-17} m²/s. This is somewhat smaller than the value of $\sim 10^{-15}$ m²/s reported for K⁺ diffusion in Sb₂S₃.⁸³ Compared to the expected range of D_{AM} values for Li and Na ion in 2D materials ($\sim 10^{-19}$ - 10^{-13} m²/s)⁷³, these values are not particularly high, indicating that As₂S₃ (or indeed Sb₂S₃) is not best suited to achieving good rate performance. However, we note that this may not be such a problem in electrodes with practically relevant thickness (~ 100 μ m). Then, liquid-phase diffusion becomes dominant,⁷¹ rendering solid state diffusion much less important. Such a transition was recently mapped out for sodium-storing electrodes based on red phosphorous.⁸⁰

CONCLUSION

In this study, we have successfully achieved the exfoliation of layered As₂S₃ and fully characterized the resulting few-layered nanosheets. Combined AFM and TEM measurements showed the nanosheets to be high aspect ratio and of excellent quality. Raman spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analysis showed the nanosheet structure to be identical to that of bulk and confirmed the absence of impurities and oxides in the nanosheets.

Electrochemical characterization of As₂S₃ nanosheets as potassium ion battery anodes revealed exceptional K-storage behavior, achieving a capacity for 619 mAh/g at a current density of 50 mA/g. The electrodes demonstrated excellent cyclability, achieving a coulombic efficiency exceeding 99% after an initial activation process. The ex-situ XRD provided support for our proposed electrochemical mechanism, affirming the storage of a charge equivalent to twelve electrons per formula unit of As₂S₃. This calculation indicated a theoretical capacity of 1305 mAh/g. Furthermore, our As₂S₃@CNT electrode displayed an outstanding capacity retention of 94% after 1000 cycles at high current density of 500 mA/g. This combination of capacity and stability after long cycling is competitive with the very best results reported for electrodes based on As₂S₃-analogs, Sb₂S₃ and Bi₂S₃ based KIB anodes as displayed in Figure 6. The quantitative analysis of capacity versus rate data highlighted a close correspondence between the maximum

achievable capacity (832 mAh/g) and theoretical capacity, affirming the complete utilization of active material for ion storage. Nonetheless, we did observe a notable limitation in the rate performance, which we attributed to solid-state diffusion constraints within the nanosheets. Our analysis of electrode thickness-dependent parameters pointed to a relatively small diffusion coefficient within the inter-layer channels.

We believe the impressive theoretical capacity, high efficiency, and substantial capacity retention of these nanosheets position them as promising candidates for cutting-edge KIB application. Future research endeavors can delve deeper into the rate performance challenges, and work towards unlocking the full potential of these nanosheets for practical energy storage applications.

METHODS

Exfoliation: The As_2S_3 crystal was ground into chunks of powder which was bath-sonicated in 2-propanol for 30 min at a frequency of 37 MHz, at ambient temperature. This results in a light-yellow dispersion, with chunks of powder at the bottom of the vial, which were collected for the inert liquid-phase exfoliation procedure. This step ensures removal of any surface impurities if present. For the inert-gas exfoliation liquid phase exfoliation process, the cleaned chunks of powder were bath sonicated in an argon-atmosphere for 10 hours, in a dried, distilled, and degassed 2-propanol. The initial starting concentration was kept at 2mg/ml. A round-bottom flask was used in the sonication process (Branson ultrasonic bath, CPX2800-E, 130 W). The dispersion was cooled periodically by exchanging the bath water with ice-cooled water every 30 minutes to maintain a temperature $< 10^\circ C$. Following sonication, the obtained dispersion underwent two consecutive centrifugation steps. The first step involved centrifugation at 220g for 2 hours aimed at removing large and thick unexfoliated particles. The supernatant obtained after this step was separated from sediment under inert atmosphere and subjected to a second centrifugation step at 3800g for 3 hours. This step ensures the removal of impurities and defective nanomaterial that typically present in the supernatant at higher speeds, leaving pristine few-layered nanosheets in the sediment. The sediment was then re-dispersed in fresh 2-propanol solvent, and the concentration was carefully measured. This is referred to as standard sample.

Electrode formation: In the first step, a dispersion of single-walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT) was prepared in 2-propanol with the goal of achieving a concentration of < 0.1 mg/ml to prevent nanotube aggregation in the obtained dispersion. To achieve this, 8 mg of P3-SWCNT were

suspended in 80 ml of 2-propanol, and the resulting solution underwent probe sonication for 3 hours using a horn-tip sonic probe (Vibracell CVX, 750W). The amplitude was set at 50% with a pulse duration of 6s on/2s off. The temperature was carefully maintained at $< 10^{\circ}\text{C}$ throughout the probe sonication process by employing ice-cooling. The outcome of this process was a black dispersion, which was allowed to free-stand for 2 hours. Afterwards, the top two-thirds of the dispersion were separated, and its final concentration was measured via filtering, resulting in a concentration of 0.085 mg/ml. In the second step, the standard exfoliated dispersion of As_2S_3 was mixed with the SWCNT dispersion in the weight ratio of 70:30 and was bath sonicated for 30 minutes to ensure uniform mixing. In the final step, the resultant mixture was vacuum filtered using Celgard 2320 membrane with thickness, 20 μm and area of 2 cm^2 . This resulted in a free-standing nanocomposite film that would be utilized as an electrode. This resultant film was subsequently cut into the area of 0.178 cm^2 , which was required for electrochemical testing. The areal mass-loading of As_2S_3 electrodes was calculated by using the thickness obtained from SEM cross-sectional measurement, along with the area, and mass of the electrode, yielding a value of 0.44 mg/cm^2 .

Assembly of K-ion half cell: K-ion half cells were assembled using CR-2032 type coin cells (14 mm; MTI Corp.) in a glovebox filled with argon, ensuring O_2 and H_2O levels were maintained below 0.1 ppm. Potassium metal pieces, initially soaked in mineral oil within the glovebox, were wiped clean to remove the oil. Subsequently, the metal pieces were cut and sliced with a blade to expose fresh metal surfaces and then rolled into flat discs for used as counter/reference electrodes. Whatman glass fiber filters (GD/D, diameter 90mm) were employed as separators. The electrolyte consisted of potassium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (KFSI, 2 M) dissolved in triethyl phosphate (TEP). After assembly within the glove box, the cells were removed and placed in an oven at 40°C for 24 hours before conducting electrochemical measurements.

Characterization: The UV-Visible extinction and absorption measurements were conducted using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050 spectrometer within the wavelength range of 250 to 800 nm. Quartz cuvettes with a 4 mm pathlength were employed for this purpose. The concentration of the dispersion was determined by filtering and weighing membranes (Celgard 2320) to calculate the extinction coefficient spectra. For absorbance spectra, a setup utilizing an integration sphere with a radius of 150 mm was employed. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging was

performed using a JEOL 2100 instrument on holey carbon grids (400 mesh) with an accelerating voltage of 200 KV. High resolution TEM and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) were carried out using FEI TITAN G2 80-300 microscope operated in STEM mode at 300kV acceleration. Multi-frame ADF STEM image series were recorded using the Fischione model 3000 ADF detector before rigid and non-rigid registration using the SmartAlign software from HREM Research (Tokyo).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectra were obtained with a Bruker D8 Discover high-resolution diffractometer equipped with a copper tube emitting K_{α} radiation (wavelength of 1.5406 Å) and a double-bounce Ge [220] monochromator. The spectra were acquired in the 2θ range from 10 to 80 on films prepared on silicon (100) wafers, and on electrodes (fresh free-standing electrode, electrode on Cu foil after it has run 200 GCD cycles, and electrodes which are potassiated and de-potassiated to different voltages).

Raman spectroscopy was conducted using a Horiba Jobin Yvon Lab RAM ARAMIS instrument in ambient conditions, both on bulk crystals and films made on silicon wafer by drop-cast method using dispersion containing nanosheets. A 532 nm laser with an adjustable power was used to excite the samples with a 100X objective. A grating with 1800 grooves per millimeter dispersed the signal onto the CCD detector maintained at -70°C . Samples were prepared by drop-casting dispersion onto silicon wafers which are heated at 50°C .

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was carried out using a Bruker multimode 8 microscope in ScanAsyst mode, employing OLTESPA R3 cantilever. The samples for AFM are prepared by drop casting a diluted dispersion on silicon wafers and heating it at 60°C , followed by drying using argon gas.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed using a Carl ZEISS Ultra Plus SEM. Samples were mounted on aluminium SEM stubs using conductive carbon tabs (Ted Pella) and grounded using conductive silver paint (PELCO, Ted Pella). All images were captured at an accelerating voltage of 2 kV using a working distance of 5 mm and a 30 μm aperture. Both the Inlens and SE2 detectors were used for imaging. Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was performed using a 20mm² Oxford INCA EDX detector. Cross-sectional SEM images of battery electrodes were taken pre- and post-cycling by fracturing the free-standing electrodes. The average electrode

thickness was determined by measuring the electrode thickness from SEM cross-sections across the electrode.

FIGURES

Figure 1: Characterization of liquid phase exfoliated As_2S_3 . (A) Photograph of the mineral orpiment. (B) Crystal structure of bulk As_2S_3 , composed of covalently bonded ruffled sheets of As_2S_3 oriented in the (010) direction, held together by weak Van der Waals forces. Arsenic and sulfur atoms are depicted as purple and yellow spheres, respectively. The unit cell is represented with a black box, consists of 2 layers with a total of 20 atoms. (C) SEM image of the orpiment crystal surface (as shown in A) displaying multilayered sheets. (D) Dispersed As_2S_3 nanosheets in solvent 2-propanol obtained after liquid phase exfoliation in inert atmosphere. (E) Optical extinction, absorbance, and scattering coefficient spectra of the dispersion versus wavelength. (F) TEM images of As_2S_3 nanosheets. (G) Raman spectra comparison between bulk and exfoliated As_2S_3 .

Figure 2: Structure and aspect ratio analysis of As_2S_3 nanosheets. (A) X-ray diffractogram of both bulk crystal and exfoliated nanosheets. Diffraction peaks are indexed using PDF card number 01-071-2435 (Crystal system: Monoclinic, space group: $P2_1/n$). (B) TEM image of an As_2S_3 nanosheet with the corresponding selected area diffraction pattern (C). The nanosheet is oriented along the [010] direction, parallel to the As_2S_3 crystal cleavage plane. A full assignment of the diffraction spot pattern can be found in the supplementary information. (D) Atomic-force microscopy image of As_2S_3 nanosheets deposited on a substrate. (E) Distribution plots illustrating the thickness and length of nanosheets. More than 100 nanosheets were individually measured for length, width, and step height, exhibiting a log-normal distribution as indicated by the dotted curve. The aspect ratio of each nanosheet, defined as the ratio of its length to thickness, was calculated and is depicted in distribution plot (F). The mean thickness, length, and aspect ratio are reported in the plot along with standard errors.

Figure 3: Investigation of the electrochemical mechanism in few-layered nanosheets of As₂S₃ (70 wt%) and CNT (30 wt%) nanocomposite anode for KIB. (A) Cross-sectional SEM image of the As₂S₃ electrode with a mass-loading of 0.44 mg/cm² and a thickness of 4.6 μm. (B) SEM image revealing the interconnected network of nanosheets and carbon nanotubes on the electrode surface. (C) The initial five cycling voltammetry (CV) curves acquired at a scan rate of 0.1 mV/s. (D) Voltage profiles for the galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) for first five cycles recorded at a current density of 200 mA/g and the corresponding differential voltage plots (E). (F) Charge-discharge cycling and coulombic efficiency performance of the electrode at 200 mA/g, demonstrating an increase in specific capacity (normalized to the active mass represented as Q/M_{act}) with cycle number, plateauing after 124 cycles.

Figure 4: Post-cycling analysis for studying the effect of extended activation on As_2S_3 (70 wt%) and CNT (30 wt%) nanocomposites as KIB anodes. (A) Differential voltage curves collected during the extended activation processes at a current density of 200 mA/g, for 5th, 50th, 100th, 124th, 155th, 180th and 200th cycles. (B) CV curves of the As_2S_3/CNT composite electrode before and after the extended activation processes. (C) X-ray diffraction pattern of As_2S_3/CNT composite anodes at potassiated and de-potassiated state. (D) SEM images of the As_2S_3/CNT composite electrode after the extended activation processes.

Figure 5: Electrochemical properties of few-layered $As_2S_3@CNT$ electrode. (A) The discharge and charge curves at 50 mA/g for the initial five cycles after extended electrode activation. (B) Rate capability of electrode at different current densities. (C) Long cycling performance at 500 mA/g. Inset shows the coulombic efficiency (%) with cycle number. (D) Specific capacity plotted versus rate, R ($R = (I/M_{Act})/(Q/M_{Act})$) for the electrode. The fit is to Equation (1) with the fit parameters given in the panel.

Figure 6: Comparative analysis of maximum specific capacity ($Q/M_{act} (max)$), cycle number, and capacity retention between finding of this study and those reported for Sb_2S_3 and Bi_2S_3 in the literature. For list of references, refer to table 2 in the supplementary information.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. The following file is available for free of charge.

A. SAED pattern, EDX and Step-height analysis of exfoliated nanosheets of As_2S_3 ; B. Free-standing, electrochemical performance of SWCNTs electrode, post cycling analysis of $As_2S_3@CNT$ electrodes and Voltage profiles; C. Literature comparison of this work with others

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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REFERENCES

- (1) Liang, Y.; Zhao, C. Z.; Yuan, H.; Chen, Y.; Zhang, W.; Huang, J. Q.; Yu, D.; Liu, Y.; Titirici, M. M.; Chueh, Y. L. A review of rechargeable batteries for portable electronic devices. *InfoMat* **2019**, *1* (1), 6-32 %@ 2567-3165.
- (2) Eftekhari, A. Lithium batteries for electric vehicles: from economy to research strategy. ACS Publications: 2019.
- (3) Diouf, B.; Pode, R. Potential of lithium-ion batteries in renewable energy. *Renewable Energy* **2015**, *76*, 375-380 %@ 0960-1481.
- (4) Zubi, G.; Dufo-López, R.; Carvalho, M.; Pasaoglu, G. The lithium-ion battery: State of the art and future perspectives. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **2018**, *89*, 292-308 %@ 1364-0321.
- (5) Christmann, P.; Gloaguen, E.; Labbé, J.-F.; Melleton, J.; Piantone, P. Global lithium resources and sustainability issues. In *Lithium process chemistry*, Elsevier, 2015; pp 1-40.
- (6) Peters, J. F.; Weil, M. A critical assessment of the resource depletion potential of current and future lithium-ion batteries. *Resources* **2016**, *5* (4), 46 %@ 2079-9276.
- (7) Zhang, W.; Lu, J.; Guo, Z. Challenges and future perspectives on sodium and potassium ion batteries for grid-scale energy storage. *Materials Today* **2021**, *50*, 400-417 %@ 1369-7021.
- (8) Mohan, I.; Raj, A.; Shubham, K.; Lata, D. B.; Mandal, S.; Kumar, S. Potential of potassium and sodium-ion batteries as the future of energy storage: Recent progress in anodic materials. *Journal of Energy Storage* **2022**, *55*, 105625 %@ 102352-105152X.
- (9) Kubota, K.; Dahbi, M.; Hosaka, T.; Kumakura, S.; Komaba, S. Towards K-ion and Na-ion batteries as “beyond Li-ion”. *The chemical record* **2018**, *18* (4), 459-479 %@ 1527-8999.
- (10) Biemolt, J.; Jungbacker, P.; van Teijlingen, T.; Yan, N.; Rothenberg, G. Beyond lithium-based batteries. *Materials* **2020**, *13* (2), 425 %@ 1996-1944.
- (11) Liu, Y.; Liu, X.; Wang, T.; Fan, L.-Z.; Jiao, L. Research and application progress on key materials for sodium-ion batteries. *Sustainable Energy & Fuels* **2017**, *1* (5), 986-1006.

- (12) Bin, D.; Wang, F.; Tamirat, A. G.; Suo, L.; Wang, Y.; Wang, C.; Xia, Y. Progress in aqueous rechargeable sodium-ion batteries. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2018**, *8* (17), 1703008 %@ 1701614-1706832.
- (13) Rajagopalan, R.; Tang, Y.; Ji, X.; Jia, C.; Wang, H. Advancements and challenges in potassium ion batteries: a comprehensive review. *Advanced Functional Materials* **2020**, *30* (12), 1909486 %@ 1901616-1909301X.
- (14) Pramudita, J. C.; Sehwat, D.; Goonetilleke, D.; Sharma, N. An initial review of the status of electrode materials for potassium-ion batteries. *Advanced energy materials* **2017**, *7* (24), 1602911 %@ 1601614-1606832.
- (15) Zhang, X.; Yang, D.; Rui, X.; Yu, Y.; Huang, S. Advanced cathodes for potassium-ion battery. *Current Opinion in Electrochemistry* **2019**, *18*, 24-30 %@ 2451-9103.
- (16) Zheng, J.; Wu, Y.; Sun, Y.; Rong, J.; Li, H.; Niu, L. Advanced anode materials of potassium ion batteries: from zero dimension to three dimensions. *Nano-Micro Letters* **2021**, *13*, 1-37 %@ 2311-6706.
- (17) Chen, K. S.; Balla, I.; Luu, N. S.; Hersam, M. C. Emerging Opportunities for Two-Dimensional Materials in Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Acs Energy Letters* **2017**, *2* (9), 2026-2034. DOI: 10.1021/acseenergylett.7b00476.
- (18) Liu, Q.; Hu, Z.; Chen, M.; Zou, C.; Jin, H.; Wang, S.; Chou, S. L.; Dou, S. X. Recent progress of layered transition metal oxide cathodes for sodium-ion batteries. *Small* **2019**, *15* (32), 1805381 %@ 1801613-1806810.
- (19) Zhang, C.; Pan, H.; Sun, L.; Xu, F.; Ouyang, Y.; Rosei, F. Progress and perspectives of 2D materials as anodes for potassium-ion batteries. *Energy Storage Materials* **2021**, *38*, 354-378 %@ 2405-8297.
- (20) Miró, P.; Audiffred, M.; Heine, T. An atlas of two-dimensional materials. *Chemical Society Reviews* **2014**, *43* (18), 6537-6554.
- (21) Coleman, J. N.; Lotya, M.; O'Neill, A.; Bergin, S. D.; King, P. J.; Khan, U.; Young, K.; Gaucher, A.; De, S.; Smith, R. J. Two-dimensional nanosheets produced by liquid exfoliation of layered materials. *Science* **2011**, *331* (6017), 568-571 %@ 0036-8075.
- (22) Nicolosi, V.; Chhowalla, M.; Kanatzidis, M. G.; Strano, M. S.; Coleman, J. N. Liquid exfoliation of layered materials. *Science* **2013**, *340* (6139), 1226419 %@ 1220036-1228075.
- (23) Backes, C.; Szydłowska, B. M.; Harvey, A.; Yuan, S. J.; Vega-Mayoral, V.; Davies, B. R.; Zhao, P. L.; Hanlon, D.; Santos, E. J. G.; Katsnelson, M. I.; et al. Production of Highly Monolayer Enriched Dispersions of Liquid-Exfoliated Nanosheets by Liquid Cascade Centrifugation. *Acs Nano* **2016**, *10* (1), 1589-1601. DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.5b07228.
- (24) Chen, K.-S.; Balla, I.; Luu, N. S.; Hersam, M. C. Emerging opportunities for two-dimensional materials in lithium-ion batteries. *ACS Energy Letters* **2017**, *2* (9), 2026-2034 %@ 2380-8195.
- (25) Peng, L.; Zhu, Y.; Chen, D.; Ruoff, R. S.; Yu, G. Two-dimensional materials for beyond-lithium-ion batteries. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2016**, *6* (11), 1600025 %@ 1601614-1606832.
- (26) Pomerantseva, E.; Gogotsi, Y. Two-dimensional heterostructures for energy storage. *Nature Energy* **2017**, *2* (7), 1-6 %@ 2058-7546.
- (27) Sultana, I.; Rahman, M. M.; Ramireddy, T.; Chen, Y.; Glushenkov, A. M. High capacity potassium-ion battery anodes based on black phosphorus. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2017**, *5* (45), 23506-23512.
- (28) Fang, L.; Xu, J.; Sun, S.; Lin, B.; Guo, Q.; Luo, D.; Xia, H. Few-layered tin sulfide nanosheets supported on reduced graphene oxide as a high-performance anode for potassium-ion batteries. *Small* **2019**, *15* (10), 1804806 %@ 1801613-1806810.
- (29) Jia, B.; Yu, Q.; Zhao, Y.; Qin, M.; Wang, W.; Liu, Z.; Lao, C. Y.; Liu, Y.; Wu, H.; Zhang, Z. Bamboo-like hollow tubes with MoS₂/N-doped-C interfaces boost potassium-ion storage. *Advanced Functional Materials* **2018**, *28* (40), 1803409 %@ 1801616-1803301X.
- (30) Yao, K.; Xu, Z.; Ma, M.; Li, J.; Lu, F.; Huang, J. Densified metallic MoS₂/graphene enabling fast potassium-ion storage with superior gravimetric and volumetric capacities. *Advanced Functional Materials* **2020**, *30* (24), 2001484 %@ 2001616-2001301X.

- (31) Zhang, P.; Zhu, Q.; Wei, Y.; Xu, B. Achieving stable and fast potassium storage of Sb₂S₃@ MXene anode via interfacial bonding and electrolyte chemistry. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2023**, *451*, 138891-138947.
- (32) Cheng, Y.; Yao, Z.; Zhang, Q.; Chen, J.; Ye, W.; Zhou, S.; Liu, H.; Wang, M. S. In situ atomic-scale observation of reversible potassium storage in Sb₂S₃@ carbon nanowire anodes. *Advanced Functional Materials* **2020**, *30* (52), 2005417-2005501.
- (33) Wang, C.; Lu, J.; Tong, H.; Wu, S.; Wang, D.; Liu, B.; Cheng, L.; Lin, Z.; Hu, L.; Wang, H. Structural engineering of sulfur-doped carbon encapsulated bismuth sulfide core-shell structure for enhanced potassium storage performance. *Nano Research* **2021**, *14* (10), 3545-3551.
- (34) Cheng, H. F.; Zhou, Y.; Frost, R. L. Structure comparison of Orpiment and Realgar by Raman spectroscopy. *Spectroscopy Letters* **2017**, *50* (1), 23-29. DOI: 10.1080/00387010.2016.1277359.
- (35) Carroll, E.; Buckley, D.; Mogili, N. V. V.; McNulty, D.; Sergio Moreno, M.; Glynn, C.; Collins, G.; Holmes, J. D.; Razeeb, K. M.; O'Dwyer, C. 2D Nanosheet Paint from Solvent-Exfoliated Bi₂Te₃ Ink. *Chemistry of Materials* **2017**, *29* (17), 7390-7400, Article. DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.7b02321.
- (36) Hindmarsh, J. T.; McCurdy, R. F.; Savory, J. Clinical and environmental aspects of arsenic toxicity. *CRC Critical Reviews in Clinical Laboratory Sciences* **1986**, *23* (4), 315-347.
- (37) Kapp, R. W. Arsenic: Toxicology and Health Effects. In *Encyclopedia of Food and Health*, Caballero, B., Finglas, P. M., Toldrá, F. Eds.; Academic Press, 2016; pp 256-265.
- (38) Lim, Y. R.; Shojaei, F.; Park, K.; Jung, C. S.; Park, J.; Cho, W. I.; Kang, H. S. Arsenic for high-capacity lithium- and sodium-ion batteries. *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10* (15), 7047-7057, 10.1039/C8NR00276B. DOI: 10.1039/C8NR00276B.
- (39) Luxa, J.; Bouša, D.; Zoller, F.; Fattakhova-Rohlfing, D.; Sofer, Z. Black phosphorus–arsenic alloys for lithium ion batteries. *FlatChem* **2020**, *19*, 100143. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flatc.2019.100143>.
- (40) Morimoto, N. The crystal structure of orpiment (As₂S₃) refined. *Mineralogical Journal* **1954**, *1* (3), 160-169.
- (41) Šiškins, M.; Lee, M.; Alijani, F.; Van Blankenstein, M. R.; Davidovikj, D.; Van Der Zant, H. S. J.; Steeneken, P. G. Highly anisotropic mechanical and optical properties of 2D layered As₂S₃ membranes. *ACS nano* **2019**, *13* (9), 10845-10851.
- (42) Debbichi, L.; Kim, H.; Björkman, T.; Eriksson, O.; Lebègue, S. First-principles investigation of two-dimensional trichalcogenide and sesquichalcogenide monolayers. *Physical Review B* **2016**, *93* (24), 245307.
- (43) Frost, R. L.; Martens, W. N.; Klopogge, J. T. Raman spectroscopic study of cinnabar (HgS), realgar (As₄S₄), and orpiment (As₂S₃) at 298 and 77K. *Neues Jahrbuch für Mineralogie-Monatshefte* **2002**, 469-480.
- (44) Mamedov, S.; Drichko, N. Characterization of 2D As₂S₃ crystal by Raman spectroscopy. *MRS Advances* **2018**, *3* (6-7), 385-390.
- (45) Razzetti, C.; Lottici, P. P. Polarization analysis of the Raman spectrum of As₂S₃ crystals. *Solid State Communications* **1979**, *29* (4), 361-364.
- (46) Backes, C.; Paton, K. R.; Hanlon, D.; Yuan, S.; Katsnelson, M. I.; Houston, J.; Smith, R. J.; McCloskey, D.; Donegan, J. F.; Coleman, J. N. Spectroscopic metrics allow in situ measurement of mean size and thickness of liquid-exfoliated few-layer graphene nanosheets. *Nanoscale* **2016**, *8* (7), 4311-4323.
- (47) Hernandez, Y.; Nicolosi, V.; Lotya, M.; Blighe, F. M.; Sun, Z.; De, S.; McGovern, I. T.; Holland, B.; Byrne, M.; Gun'ko, Y. K. High-yield production of graphene by liquid-phase exfoliation of graphite. *Nature nanotechnology* **2008**, *3* (9), 563-568.
- (48) Harvey, A.; Backes, C.; Boland, J. B.; He, X.; Griffin, A.; Szydłowska, B.; Gabbett, C.; Donegan, J. F.; Coleman, J. N. Non-resonant light scattering in dispersions of 2D nanosheets. *Nature communications* **2018**, *9* (1), 4553.

- (49) Griffin, A.; Harvey, A.; Cunningham, B.; Scullion, D.; Tian, T.; Shih, C.-J.; Gruening, M.; Donegan, J. F.; Santos, E. J. G.; Backes, C. Spectroscopic size and thickness metrics for liquid-exfoliated h-BN. *Chemistry of Materials* **2018**, *30* (6), 1998-2005 %@ 0897-4756.
- (50) Holder, C. F.; Schaak, R. E. Tutorial on powder X-ray diffraction for characterizing nanoscale materials. In *Acs Nano*, ACS Publications: 2019; Vol. 13, pp 7359-7365 %@ 1936-0851.
- (51) Liu, K.; Dai, L.; Li, H.; Hu, H.; Yang, L.; Pu, C.; Hong, M.; Liu, P. Phase transition and metallization of orpiment by Raman spectroscopy, electrical conductivity and theoretical calculation under high pressure. *Materials* **2019**, *12* (5), 784 %@ 1996-1944.
- (52) Zaumseil, P. High-resolution characterization of the forbidden Si 200 and Si 222 reflections. *Journal of applied crystallography* **2015**, *48* (2), 528-532 %@ 1600-5767.
- (53) Backes, C.; Campi, D.; Szydłowska, B. M.; Synnatschke, K.; Ojala, E.; Rashvand, F.; Harvey, A.; Griffin, A.; Sofer, Z.; Marzari, N. Equipartition of energy defines the size–thickness relationship in liquid-exfoliated nanosheets. *ACS nano* **2019**, *13* (6), 7050-7061 %@ 1936-0851.
- (54) Coleman, J. N. Are Nanotube Networks the Key to High-Rate, High Capacity Lithium Ion Batteries? 2020; The Electrochemical Society, Inc.: pp 589-589 %@ 2151-2043.
- (55) Park, S.-H.; King, P. J.; Tian, R.; Boland, C. S.; Coelho, J.; Zhang, C.; McBean, P.; McEvoy, N.; Kremer, M. P.; Daly, D. High areal capacity battery electrodes enabled by segregated nanotube networks. *Nature Energy* **2019**, *4* (7), 560-567 %@ 2058-7546.
- (56) Gabbett, C.; Doolan¹, L.; Synnatschke, K.; Gambini, L.; Coleman, E.; Kelly, A. G.; Liu, S.; Caffrey, E.; Munuera, J.; Murphy, C.; et al. Morphological Characterisation of Printed Nanostructured Networks using High-resolution 3D FIB-SEM Nanotomography. *Nature Communications (in press)* **2023**.
- (57) Wang, J.; Fan, L.; Liu, Z.; Chen, S.; Zhang, Q.; Wang, L.; Yang, H.; Yu, X.; Lu, B. In situ alloying strategy for exceptional potassium ion batteries. *ACS nano* **2019**, *13* (3), 3703-3713 %@ 1936-0851.
- (58) Nithya, C.; Modigunta, J. K. R.; In, I.; Kim, S.; Gopukumar, S. Bi₂S₃ Nanorods Deposited on Reduced Graphene Oxide for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Nano Materials* **2023**, *6* (7), 6121-6132 %@ 2574-0970.
- (59) Liu, Y.; Tai, Z.; Zhang, J.; Pang, W. K.; Zhang, Q.; Feng, H.; Konstantinov, K.; Guo, Z.; Liu, H. K. Boosting potassium-ion batteries by few-layered composite anodes prepared via solution-triggered one-step shear exfoliation. *Nature communications* **2018**, *9* (1), 3645 %@ 2041-1723.
- (60) Zhou, J.; Wang, L.; Yang, M.; Wu, J.; Chen, F.; Huang, W.; Han, N.; Ye, H.; Zhao, F.; Li, Y. Hierarchical VS₂ nanosheet assemblies: a universal host material for the reversible storage of alkali metal ions. *Advanced Materials* **2017**, *29* (35), 1702061 %@ 1700935-1709648.
- (61) Nithya, C.; Modigunta, J. K. R.; In, I.; Kim, S.; Gopukumar, S. Bi₂S₃ Nanorods Deposited on Reduced Graphene Oxide for Potassium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Applied Nano Materials* **2023**, *6* (7), 6121-6132. DOI: 10.1021/acsnm.3c00437.
- (62) Gu, S.; Xiao, N.; Wu, F.; Bai, Y.; Wu, C.; Wu, Y. Chemical synthesis of K₂S₂ and K₂S₃ for probing electrochemical mechanisms in K–S batteries. *ACS Energy Letters* **2018**, *3* (12), 2858-2864 %@ 2380-8195.
- (63) Du, Y.; Zhang, Z.; Xu, Y.; Bao, J.; Zhou, X. Metal sulfide-based potassium-ion battery anodes: storage mechanisms and synthesis strategies. *Acta Phys.-Chim. Sin* **2022**, *38*, 2205017.
- (64) Cao, L.; Luo, B.; Xu, B.; Zhang, J.; Wang, C.; Xiao, Z.; Li, S.; Li, Y.; Zhang, B.; Zou, G. Stabilizing intermediate phases via efficient entrapment effects of layered VS₄/SnS@C heterostructure for ultralong lifespan potassium-ion batteries. *Advanced Functional Materials* **2021**, *31* (36), 2103802 %@ 2101616-2103301X.
- (65) Shpotyuk, O.; Demchenko, P.; Shpotyuk, Y.; Bujňáková, Z.; Baláž, P. Medium-range structural changes in glassy As₂S₃ driven by high-energy mechanical milling. *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **2019**, *505*, 347-353 %@ 0022-3093.
- (66) Konkena, B.; Kaur, H.; Tian, R.; Gabbett, C.; McCrystall, M.; Horvath, D. V.; Synnatschke, K.; Roy, A.; Smith, R.; Nicolosi, V. Liquid Processing of Interfacially Grown Iron-Oxide Flowers into 2D-Platelets Yields

Lithium-Ion Battery Anodes with Capacities of Twice the Theoretical Value. *Small* **2022**, *18* (39), 2203918 %@ 2201613-2206810.

(67) Fan, H.-N.; Wang, X.-Y.; Yu, H.-B.; Gu, Q.-F.; Chen, S.-L.; Liu, Z.; Chen, X.-H.; Luo, W.-B.; Liu, H.-K. Enhanced Potassium Ion Battery by Inducing Interlayer Anionic Ligands in MoS_{1.5}Se_{0.5} Nanosheets with Exploration of the Mechanism. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2020**, *10* (21), 1904162. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201904162>.

(68) Ma, X.; Fu, H.; Shen, J.; Zhang, D.; Zhou, J.; Tong, C.; Rao, A. M.; Zhou, J.; Fan, L.; Lu, B. Green Ether Electrolytes for Sustainable High-voltage Potassium Ion Batteries. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2023**, *62* (49), e202312973 %@ 202311433-202317851.

(69) Geng, Y.; Fu, H.; Hu, Y.; Rao, A. M.; Fan, L.; Zhou, J.; Lu, B. Molecular-level design for a phosphate-based electrolyte for stable potassium-ion batteries. *Applied Physics Letters* **2024**, *124* (6 %@ 0003-6951).

(70) Fan, L.; Xie, H.; Hu, Y.; Caixiang, Z.; Rao, A. M.; Zhou, J.; Lu, B. A tailored electrolyte for safe and durable potassium ion batteries. *Energy & Environmental Science* **2023**, *16* (1), 305-315.

(71) Horvath, D. V.; Coelho, J.; Tian, R.; Nicolosi, V.; Coleman, J. N. Quantifying the Dependence of Battery Rate Performance on Electrode Thickness. *Acs Applied Energy Materials* **2020**, *3* (10), 10154-10163. DOI: 10.1021/acsaem.0c01865.

(72) Tian, R.; Alcalá, N.; O'Neill, S. J. K.; Horvath, D. V.; Coelho, J.; Griffin, A. J.; Zhang, Y.; Nicolosi, V.; O'Dwyer, C.; Coleman, J. N. Quantifying the Effect of Electronic Conductivity on the Rate Performance of Nanocomposite Battery Electrodes. *Acs Applied Energy Materials* **2020**, *3* (3), 2966-2974. DOI: 10.1021/acsaem.0c00034.

(73) Tian, R.; Breshears, M.; Horvath, D. V.; Coleman, J. N. The Rate Performance of Two-Dimensional Material-Based Battery Electrodes May Not Be as Good as Commonly Believed. *ACS Nano* **2020**, *14* (3), 3129-3140. DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.9b08304.

(74) Tian, R.; Park, S.-H.; King, P. J.; Cunningham, G.; Coelho, J.; Nicolosi, V.; Coleman, J. N. Quantifying the factors limiting rate performance in battery electrodes. *Nature Communications* **2019**, *10* (1), 1933. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-019-09792-9.

(75) Horvath, D. V.; Tian, R.; Gabbett, C.; Nicolosi, V.; Coleman, J. N. Quantifying the Effect of Separator Thickness on Rate Performance in Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* **2022**, *169* (3). DOI: 10.1149/1945-7111/ac5654.

(76) Park, S.-H.; Tian, R.; Coelho, J.; Nicolosi, V.; Coleman, J. N. Quantifying the Trade-Off between Absolute Capacity and Rate Performance in Battery Electrodes. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2019**, *9* (33). DOI: 10.1002/aenm.201901359.

(77) Coleman, J. N.; Tian, R. Developing models to fit capacity-rate data in battery systems. *Current Opinion in Electrochemistry* **2020**, *21*, 1-6, Review. DOI: 10.1016/j.coelec.2019.12.003.

(78) Tian, R.; Griffin, A.; McCrystall, M.; Breshears, M.; Harvey, A.; Gabbett, C.; Horváth, D. V.; Backes, C.; Jing, Y.; Heine, T.; et al. Liquid Exfoliated SnP₃ Nanosheets for Very High Areal Capacity Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2021**, *11* (4), 2002364. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202002364>.

(79) Konkena, B.; Kaur, H.; Tian, R.; Gabbett, C.; McCrystall, M.; Horvath, D. V.; Synnatschke, K.; Roy, A.; Smith, R.; Nicolosi, V.; et al. Liquid Processing of Interfacially Grown Iron-Oxide Flowers into 2D-Platelets Yields Lithium-Ion Battery Anodes with Capacities of Twice the Theoretical Value. *Small* **2022**, *18* (39), 2203918. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.202203918>.

(80) Kaur, H.; Konkena, B.; Gabbett, C.; Smith, R.; McCrystall, M.; Tian, R.; Roy, A.; Carey, T.; Vega-Mayoral, V.; Nicolosi, V.; et al. Amorphous 2D-Nanoplatelets of Red Phosphorus Obtained by Liquid-Phase Exfoliation Yield High Areal Capacity Na-Ion Battery Anodes. *Advanced Energy Materials* **2023**, *13* (6), 2203013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202203013>.

(81) Kaur, H.; Tian, R.; Roy, A.; McCrystall, M.; Horvath, D. V.; Lozano Onrubia, G.; Smith, R.; Ruether, M.; Griffin, A.; Backes, C.; et al. Production of Quasi-2D Platelets of Nonlayered Iron Pyrite (FeS₂) by Liquid-

Phase Exfoliation for High Performance Battery Electrodes. *ACS Nano* **2020**, *14* (10), 13418-13432. DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.0c05292.

(82) Chen, T.; Kaur, H.; McCrystall, M.; Tian, R.; Roy, A.; Smith, R.; Horvath, D. V.; Maughan, J.; Konkana, B.; Venkatesan, M.; et al. Liquid phase exfoliation of nonlayered non-van der Waals iron trifluoride (FeF₃) into 2D-platelets for high-capacity lithium storing cathodes. *FlatChem* **2022**, *33*, 100360. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flatc.2022.100360>.

(83) Zhang, P.; Zhu, Q.; Wei, Y.; Xu, B. Achieving stable and fast potassium storage of Sb₂S₃@MXene anode via interfacial bonding and electrolyte chemistry. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2023**, *451*, Article. DOI: 10.1016/j.cej.2022.138891.

TOC Graphic

